

GPAHRS – Navigation Enabler for More Autonomous Aircraft

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ABSTRACT:

Prototype of the new Honeywell GPS-aided MEMS based navigation system (GPAHRS) has been validated through a large flight-test campaign performed under the Clean Sky 2 Large Passenger Aircraft (LPA) Platform 3 project.

The campaign itself (more than 200 flight hours in total) was focused on the business jets (Dassault Falcon 900EX), commercial jets (Airbus A330), and regional aircrafts and various flight test scenarios.

This paper provides an overview of the GPAHRS system itself, its integration within the Flight Test Bed (FTB) equipment, and most importantly, performance (in terms of accuracy and integrity) validation of results obtained during the campaign.

1. INTRODUCTION

Recent trends in the aerospace industry have demonstrated a significant rise of new, innovative, and cutting-edge technologies in all relevant fields (new aircraft configurations, system integration, engines, cockpits, communication, navigation, etc.) of the aerospace industry. Those are being generally developed under various research projects and initiatives. In European Union (EU), the largest research framework for developing new disruptive technologies is the Clean Sky 2 (CS2) Joint Undertaking granted under the EU Horizon 2020 programme [1], [2], [3]. The initiative is focused on the development, integration, and demonstration of new disruptive advanced technologies for the class of Large Passenger Aircrafts (LPA).

The requirements on the new next generation aeronautic systems (CS2 LPA Platform 3) generally stem from pursuing main objective of higher level of autonomy [4].

To align with the afore-mentioned objectives, Honeywell (as a partner in the CS2 LPA Platform 3 JU) has integrated, experimentally tested, and validated the GPAHRS (GPS-aided Attitude and Heading Reference System) prototype – next-generation navigation system suitable for various categories of aircrafts. The system hybridizes information from the Micro-Electro-Mechanical Systems (MEMS) inertial sensors together with the

GPS, magnetometer, and air-data to provide additional benefits mainly in terms of performance (near navigation-grade sensors accuracy and integrity), enhanced system dissimilarity, reliability and availability, support of the permanent autopilot capability, and overall reduction of flight operations disruptions. The system is consistent with all requirements on safety as well as on operational cost reduction for the airlines and is foreseen as an important part of the future navigation systems architectures.

The experimental validation of the GPAHRS (also within the CS2 LPA Platform 3) has been performed in terms of a large flight-test campaign consisting of 37 flights (approximately 200 flight hours) in total.

The first phase (Phase-1) of the flight-test campaign was focused on the categories of the commercial jets and regional aircrafts and was performed in cooperation with Airbus on experimental A330 test aircraft (Figure 1). The overall goal was to experimentally evaluate the GPAHRS performance during the long-range flights and during the flights in “normal/typical” geographic latitudes.

Figure 1. Airbus A330 test aircraft (Source: <https://www.airbus.com/>)

The Phase-2 and Phase-3 of the campaign were focused on the business jets category of aircraft and were performed solely by Honeywell and by means of triple-engine Dassault Falcon 900EX aircraft (Figure 2), Honeywell's flight testing corporate jet. During the Phase-2 tests, the polar-flight capabilities of the GPAHRS and its achievable performance in the vicinity of Earth's geographic and geomagnetic poles were investigated. GPAHRS performance near Earth's magnetic

equator and in the areas with ionospheric/magnetic scintillations were thoroughly tested and validated during Phase-3.

Figure 2. Honeywell test A/C Dassault Falcon 900EX

The rest of the article is organized as follows: A concise description of the GPAHRS prototype is given in Section 2. Hardware equipment description and high-level block-schemes for both commercial/regional aircrafts and business jet flight-test beds is provided in Section 3. The flight-test campaign itself is addressed in Section 4. The results (in terms of position and attitude estimation errors and corresponding 1- σ estimation error bounds and protection limits) for the case of a particular trajectory are shown in Section 5. Summary of the paper can be found in Section 6.

2. GPAHRS PROTOTYPE

New Honeywell GPS-aided Attitude and Heading Reference System (GPAHRS) prototype (Figure 3) is based on hybridization of the low-cost (tactical grade) MEMS inertial sensors, GPS, magnetometer, and barometric altimeter to achieve the navigation-grade performance (when GPS is available). Integrity of the resulting navigation solution is assured by employing an integrity monitoring algorithm. When compared to navigation-grade systems with laser gyroscopes, the overall size, weight, power consumption, manufacturing complexity, and the cost of the system introduces a significant benefit for the user.

Figure 3. High-level scheme of the Honeywell GPAHRS algorithm

From the functional point of view, the system consists of the three sub-functions:

- Inertial Navigation System (INS)
- Kalman Filter (KF)
- Integrity algorithm

Within the INS sub-function, estimation of the overall aircraft's kinematics based on the IMU measurements is performed. Accelerometer measurements (appropriately levelled and compensated) are integrated once to obtain aircraft's velocity and second-time to obtain the aircraft's position. Similarly, by integrating gyroscope measurements (compensated for the gyroscope measurement errors), aircraft's attitude and heading is obtained.

When performing the corresponding integrations of IMU measurements within the INS sub-function, it is impossible to compensate for all possible error sources. Thus, the Kalman Filter sub-function is employed to utilize the GPS pseudo-range measurements, barometric altitude, as well as (calibrated) magnetometer measurements to estimate those errors and to correct the INS-based estimates of the corresponding quantities.

To detect and exclude faulty measurements from GPAHRS computations (avoiding corruption of the hybrid outputs) and to assure the integrity of the algorithm output parameters, the Honeywell proprietary integrity algorithm is employed.

3. TEST-HARDWARE CONFIGURATION

Technical equipment (Flight Test Bed, abbreviated to FTB) employed for GPAHRS validation consisted of the following sub-systems:

- Inertial sensors assembly
- National Instruments CompactRIO-based (cRIO) GPAHRS rapid prototyping platform
- Honeywell LaseRef VI inertial reference system [5]
- GNSS receivers
- Data recording systems (loggers)
- Interconnections and other infrastructure

A high-level scheme of the FTB is shown in Figure 4 below.

Figure 4. Simplified block diagram of the GPAHRS test assembly

From Figure 5, one can see that the Rack #1 consisted of the GNSS antenna splitters, power supply, 2x GNSS receivers, circuit breakers, main toggle switch and auxiliary interface (cabling). Rack #2 was comprised of 4x cRIO prototyping platforms (2 instances for data logging and 2 instances with GPAHRS algorithm itself), and interconnection (ITA) box.

Finally, the Inertial Sensors Assembly (Figure 4) was built from 2x Honeywell LaseRef VI (reference system), 2x Honeywell HG-4930 IMU [6] and 2x Honeywell KMG-7010 magnetometer.

Both racks can be seen in Figure 5. Sensor assembly is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 5. HON FTB – front view

Figure 6. HON Sensor Assembly – MEMS IMU and LaseRef VI

Figure 7. Hardware configuration for Airbus A330

Onboard Airbus' A330, the FTB was installed in the central part of the A/C as depicted in Figure 7.

In the case of Honeywell's Falcon 900EX (Figure 8 below), the two racks (Rack #1 and Rack #2) were in the front part of the cabin. Inertial Sensors Assembly (HON MEMS sensors and HON LaseRef VI reference) were placed close to the A/C centre of gravity (CoG) within the central part of the cabin.

Figure 8. Hardware configuration for HON Dassault Falcon 900EX

Magnetometers were located behind the cockpit to mitigate the impact of electromagnetic interference (EMI).

4. FLIGHT-TEST CAMPAIGN

The GPAHRS validation campaign consisted of the three parts described in the subsequent sections below.

4.1. Phase-1 (Air-Traffic/Regional Aircraft)

The first part (April 2017 – July 2017) consisted of 15 A330 flights and was performed by Airbus (based in Toulouse, France).

Figure 9. GPAHRS test hardware onboard A330

A short overview of the most important flights is given in Table 1 below. The flights differed in terms of duration, trajectory and the overall goal (interest).

Table 1. Selected Phase-1 A330 test flights

Date	Description / Interest
April 13, 2017	Toulouse to Montpellier and back Magnetometer calibration
April 24, 2017	From Toulouse over the Atlantic Ocean and back High dynamics
June 1, 2017	Toulouse to Montpellier and back Magnetometer calibration
June 13,	Toulouse to Montpellier and

2017	back
	High dynamics
June 15, 2017	From Toulouse over the Mediterranean Sea and back
	Duration of the test
June 16, 2017	Toulouse to Perpignan and back
	High dynamics
June 19, 2017	From Toulouse via Estonia and Norway to the United Kingdom and back
	Magnetic measurements and the influence of high latitudes
July 20, 2017	From Toulouse over the Atlantic Ocean and back
	High dynamics and the GPS outage
July 23, 2017	Toulouse to Switzerland
	High dynamics
July 24, 2017	Djibouti to Toulouse
	Long-range flight

From Table 1, one can see that Phase-1 was focused primarily on validating the GPAHRS performance on commercial aircraft during long-range operations, highly dynamic flight scenarios, GPS outages, as well as high-latitude operations.

Figure 10. Trajectory from Toulouse to Perpignan and back from the Phase-1

The data captured during the campaign consisted of both dynamic (in-the-flight) data and static (on-the-ground) data.

4.2. Phase-2 (Business Jet)

The second part of the campaign took place in October 2018 and was based both in Brno, Czech Republic and Phoenix, AZ, USA. The campaign was performed solely by Honeywell's Dassault Falcon 900EX aircraft, pilots and engineers.

Figure 11. Holding-pattern trajectory (Flight #05) from the Phase-2

Figure 11 illustrates the holding-pattern-trajectory with approaches as flown from Brno to Karlovy Vary (Czech Republic).

Among the main goals of this part (Phase-2) was to test the capabilities of the GPAHRS in high latitudes (polar regions) and when flying directly over the Earth's north pole and in the vicinity of north geomagnetic pole (Figure 12).

Table 2. Selected Phase-2 Falcon 900EX test flights

Flight #	Description / Interest
01	Phoenix, AZ to Fairbanks, AK Relocation and preparation
02	Fairbanks, AK to Ivalo (Finland) Flight over the North Pole
03	Ivalo (Finland) to London (UK) Relocation and start of the HON European flight test campaign
04	Porto (Portugal) to Brno (Czech Republic) Part of the HON European flight test campaign
05	Brno (Czech Republic) to Karlovy Vary (Czech Republic) Holding patterns, dynamics and approaches

Figure 12. Polar-flight trajectory (Flight #02) from the Phase-2

This part of the campaign was devoted almost solely to the GPAHRS validation and data collection close to the magnetic equator as well as in the areas with increased occurrence of ionospheric scintillations.

Figure 14. Magnetic equator-flight trajectory (Flight #09) from the Phase-3

4.3. Phase-3 (Business Jet)

Figure 13. Magnetic equator-flight trajectory (Flight #08) from the Phase-3

The third part of the HON flight test campaign (March 2019) was based in Phoenix, AZ, USA and (similarly to the Phase-2) was performed solely by means of Honeywell equipment (Dassault Falcon 900EX aircraft) and personnel.

Table 3. Selected Phase-3 Falcon 900EX test flights

Flight #	Description / Interest
06	Phoenix, AZ
	MOPS and HDG observability
07	Phoenix, AZ
	Low box pattern flight
08	Brownsville, TX to Manaus (Brazil)
	Magnetic equator flight
09	Manaus (Brazil) to Rio de Janeiro (Brazil)
	Magnetic equator flight

Examples of the two magnetic equator-flight trajectories (Flight #08 and Flight #09) are depicted in Figure 13 and Figure 14, respectively

5. RESULTS

For this paper, the overall performance of the most important GPAHRS navigation parameters (position, attitude, and heading) were validated (in terms of estimation errors and corresponding 1- σ estimation error bounds and protection limits) and demonstrated on the Flight #05 trajectory (Figure 11) from the Phase-2 of the campaign (October 2018).

The flight departed from Brno (Czech Republic) and headed to Karlovy Vary (Czech Republic), where 40-minute holding (flying a hold) and 6 approaches were realized. On the way back, other 3 approaches were performed in Brno. the overall duration of the flight was approximately 5.7 hours.

As described in Section 3, two Honeywell LaseRef VI Micro Inertial Reference System (IRS) units were employed as the references.

5.1. Position

Position performance of the GPAHRS algorithm in latitudinal and longitudinal directions as well as in altitude is depicted in Figure 15, Figure 16, and Figure 17, respectively.

Figure 15. Latitude position error and 1- σ estimate (Holding-pattern Phase-2 Flight #05)

The overall latitude Root Mean Square (RMS) error with respect to both LaseRef VI units (henceforth, LRVI-1 and LRVI-2) was, respectively, 2.025 [m] and 1.812 [m]. Average latitude 1- σ standard deviation (STD) was 6.238 [m].

Figure 16. Longitude position error and 1- σ estimate (Holding-pattern Phase-2 Flight #05)

In longitudinal direction, the RMS error with respect to the LRVI-1 was 1.085 [m], while the error with respect to the LRVI-2 was 1.18 [m]. The average longitude 1- σ STD was 4.868 [m].

Figure 17. Altitude error and 1- σ estimate (Holding-pattern Phase-2 Flight #05)

Finally, the altitude RMS error (relative to both IRS references) was 2.423 [m] and 3.226 [m], respectively with the corresponding 1- σ STD equal to 9.85 [m].

Position accuracy of the GPARS was driven mainly by the GPS aiding and is clearly comparable to the LaseRef VI hybrid IRS performance.

5.2. Position Protection Limits

In Figure 18 and Figure 19 below, the GPAHRS position-related protection limits (PL) achieved on the Flight #05 trajectory are illustrated.

Figure 18. Horizontal position protection limit (Holding-pattern Phase-2 Flight #05)

The average GPAHRS horizontal and vertical protection limits were found to be 54.6 [m] and 73.7 [m], respectively.

Figure 19. Vertical position protection limit (Holding-pattern Phase-2 Flight #05)

5.3. Attitude and Heading

Figure 20 and Figure 21 below show the attitude accuracy of the GPAHRS algorithm.

Figure 20. Roll angle error and 1- σ estimate (Holding-pattern Phase-2 Flight #05)

For the roll angle estimates, the RMS error was 0.018 [deg] (LRVI-1) and 0.016 [deg] (LRVI-2) with average 1- σ STD equal 0.087 [deg].

Figure 21. Pitch angle error and 1- σ estimate (Holding-pattern Phase-2 Flight #05)

Similarly, the pitch angle RMS error relative to LRVI-1 was 0.013 [deg] and relative to the LRVI-2 the RMS error was 0.012 [deg]. Average pitch angle $1-\sigma$ STD was 0.086 [deg].

Like for the case of position, the overall attitude accuracy of the GPAHRS algorithm was shown to be comparable with the accuracy of the LRVI IRS reference.

Figure 22. Heading error and $1-\sigma$ estimate (Holding pattern Phase-2 Flight #05)

In Figure 22 above, the GPAHRS heading (HDG) accuracy is depicted. The HDG RMS errors are 0.488 [deg] (LRVI-1) and 0.478 [deg] (LRVI-2) with average $1-\sigma$ STD equal to 0.943 [deg].

The overall behaviour of the HDG estimates is consistent with expectations: During highly dynamic phases of flight, the accuracy of the estimates is comparable with the LRVI IRS. During the steady-flight phases, on the other hand, the accuracy of the HDG estimates degrades as expected, since driven by the magnetometer aiding.

5.4. Attitude and Heading Protection Limits

As in the case of the position, the corresponding GPAHRS attitude (Figure 23 and Figure 24) and heading (Figure 25) protection limits were computed as well. The average attitude PL were 0.51 [deg] (roll angle) and 0.51 [deg] (pitch angle).

Figure 23. Roll angle protection limit (Holding pattern Phase-2 Flight #05)

Figure 24. Pitch angle protection limit (Holding pattern Phase-2 Flight #05)

The average GPAHRS heading protection limit was found to be 5.55 [deg].

Figure 25. Heading angle protection limit (Holding pattern Phase-2 Flight #05)

6. SUMMARY

Within the CS2 LPA Platform 3 initiative, Honeywell has integrated, experimentally tested and validated new next-generation navigation system (GPAHRS) for both commercial/regional and business aircraft categories.

The overall experimental validation of the GPAHRS algorithm was performed in terms of an intensive flight-test campaign (37 flights and approx. 200 flight hours): Phase-1 (air-traffic/regional aircrafts) consisted of 15 flights (approximately 70 flight hours) and was performed in cooperation with Airbus; Phase-2 and Phase-3 (business jets) comprised of 22 flights (approximately 130 flight hours) and was performed solely by Honeywell.

In the course of the whole flight test campaign (Phase-1 to Phase-3), the GPAHRS algorithm has demonstrated its ability to operate on the expected level of required navigation performance, while satisfying all safety requirements.

Due to its dissimilarity to navigation grade systems, GPAHRS represents a new enabler of future aircraft and will provide additional navigation information source to enhance navigation system reliability and availability, to reduce flight operations disruptions, and to support permanent autopilot capability. The featured flight test campaign has shown a good consistency of GPAHRS navigation algorithm outputs and that the GPAHRS performance (if GPS available) is in most navigation parameters comparable to the navigation grade systems.

The $1-\sigma$ estimates are being rather conservative, which could be explained by conservative GPS errors modelling (mandated by DO-229/DO-316) and preliminary inertial sensor modelling (newest generation of Honeywell MEMS sensors was deployed), which gives room to tighten up the used numbers and improve the $1-\sigma$ and PL estimates.

7. ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

A/C – Aircraft
 AHRS – Attitude and Heading Reference System
 ATE – Advanced Technology Europe
 ATR - Air-Traffic/Regional (Aircraft)
 CoG – Centre of Gravity
 cRIO – National Instruments CompactRIO
 CS2 – Clean Sky 2
 EMI – Electromagnetic Interference
 EU – European Union
 FTB – Flight Test Bed
 GPS – Global Positioning System
 GPAHRS – GPS-aided Attitude and Heading Reference System
 HDG – Heading
 HON – Honeywell
 IMU – Inertial Measurement Unit
 INS – Inertial Navigation System
 IRS – Inertial Reference System
 ITA – Interchangeable Test Adapter
 JU – Joint Undertaking
 LPA – Large Passenger Aircraft
 RLVI-1 – Honeywell LaseRef VI Micro IRS #1
 RLVI-2 – Honeywell LaseRef VI Micro IRS #2
 MEMS – Micro-Electro-Mechanical System
 MOPS – Minimum Operational Performance Standard
 PL – Protection Limit
 RMS – Root Mean Square
 STD – Standard Deviation

8. REFERENCES

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